

QUOTIENT QUASI-ORDERED RESIDUATED SYSTEMS INDUCED BY QUASI-VALUATION MAPS

DANIEL A. ROMANO*

ABSTRACT. The concept of quasi-ordered residuated systems was introduced in 2018 by Bonzio and Chajda as a generalization both of commutative residuated lattices and hoop-algebras. Then this author investigated the substructures of ideals and filters in these algebraic structures. As a continuation of these research, in this article we design the concept of quotient quasi-ordered residuated systems induced by a quasi-valuation on it. Additionally, we prove some important properties of the thus constructed quotient structure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Song, Roh and Jun, in [15], introduced the notion of quasi-valuation maps based on a subalgebra and an ideal in BCK/BCI-algebras, and then they investigated several their properties. They provided relations between a quasi-valuation map based on a subalgebra and a quasi-valuation map based on an ideal. Using the notion of a quasi-valuation map based on an ideal, they constructed appropriate (pseudo) metric spaces. In [1], Aaly Kologani et al. introduced the notion of quasi-valuation maps on hoops based on subalgebras and filters and related properties of them are investigated. The idea of designing (quasi- or pseudo-) valuation maps was also applied to some other algebraic structures (for example: [9, 10, 15]). Song, Bordbar and Jun in [16], have described the quotient structure on BCK/BCI - algebras generated by a pseudo-valuation on them. Designing the quotient structure on some other algebraic structures is also shown in the papers [4, 5, 12].

Quasi-ordered residuated systems are quasi-ordered commutative residuated integral monoids ([2]). In the last few years, the theory of quasi-ordered residuated systems and related structures was enriched with more results both about the interior of these structures and about some of their substructures such as ideals and filters ([11, 13]). This class of

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algebraic structures is a generalization of both the class of commutative residuated lattices ([6, 7, 8]) and the class of hoop-algebras ([3]).

In this paper we design (Theorem 3.4) a congruence R_v on A/\equiv_{\preceq} based on a quasi-valuation map $v : A/\equiv_{\preceq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} , where $F_v = [1]_{R_v}$ holds (Theorem 3.7) with the property that the quotient A/R_v is a quasi-ordered system again (Theorem 3.5). In addition, it was shown (Theorem 3.9) that if for quasi-valuation maps v and w on a quasi-ordered residual system \mathfrak{A} the following holds $[1]_{R_v} = [1]_{R_w}$, then R_v and R_w coincide.

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, the necessary notions and notations and some of their interrelationships are listed in order to enable a reader to comfortably follow the presentation in this report. It should be pointed out here that the notations for logical conjunction, logical implication and other logical functions have a literal meaning. For example, if a formula is not closed by some quantifier, it is understood that it is under universal quantification.

2.1. Concept of quasi-ordered residuated systems. In article [2], S. Bonzio and I. Chajda introduced and analyzed the concept of residual relational systems.

Definition 2.1 ([2], Definition 2.1). A *residuated relational system* is a structure $\mathfrak{A} = \langle A, \cdot, \rightarrow, 1, R \rangle$, where $\langle A, \cdot, \rightarrow, 1 \rangle$ is an algebra of type $\langle 2, 2, 0 \rangle$ and R is a binary relation on A and satisfying the following properties:

- (1) $(A, \cdot, 1)$ is a commutative monoid;
- (2) $(\forall x \in A)((x, 1) \in R)$;
- (3) $(\forall x, y, z \in A)((x \cdot y, z) \in R \iff (x, y \rightarrow z) \in R)$.

We will refer to the operation \cdot as multiplication, to \rightarrow as its residuum and to condition (3) as residuation.

Recall that a *quasi-order relation* \preceq on a set A is a binary relation which is reflexive and transitive.

Definition 2.2 ([2]). A *quasi-ordered residuated system* is a residuated relational system $\mathfrak{A} = \langle A, \cdot, \rightarrow, 1, \preceq \rangle$, where \preceq is a quasi-order relation in the monoid (A, \cdot)

The following proposition shows the basic properties of quasi-ordered residuated systems.

Proposition 2.1 ([2], Proposition 3.1). *Let \mathfrak{A} be a quasi-ordered residuated system. Then*

- (4) *The operation \cdot preserves the pre-order in both positions;*

$$(\forall x, y, z \in A)(x \preceq y \implies (x \cdot z \preceq y \cdot z \wedge z \cdot x \preceq z \cdot y));$$

- (5) $(\forall x, y, z \in A)(x \preceq y \implies (y \rightarrow z \preceq x \rightarrow z \wedge z \rightarrow x \preceq z \rightarrow y))$;
- (6) $(\forall y, z \in A)(x \cdot (y \rightarrow z) \preceq y \rightarrow x \cdot z)$;
- (7) $(\forall x, y, z \in A)(x \cdot y \rightarrow z \preceq x \rightarrow (y \rightarrow z))$;
- (8) $(\forall x, y, z \in A)(x \rightarrow (y \rightarrow z) \preceq x \cdot y \rightarrow z)$;
- (9) $(\forall x, y, z \in A)(x \rightarrow (y \rightarrow z) \preceq y \rightarrow (x \rightarrow z))$;
- (10) $(\forall x, y, z \in A)((x \rightarrow y) \cdot (y \rightarrow z) \preceq x \rightarrow z)$;
- (11) $(\forall x, y \in A)((x \cdot y \preceq x) \wedge (x \cdot y \preceq y))$;
- (12) $(\forall x, y, z \in A)(x \rightarrow y \preceq (y \rightarrow z) \rightarrow (x \rightarrow z))$;
- (13) $(\forall x, y, z \in A)(y \rightarrow z \preceq (x \rightarrow y) \rightarrow (x \rightarrow z))$.

It is generally known that a quasi-order relation \preceq on a set A generates an equivalence relation $\equiv_{\preceq} := \preceq \cap \preceq^{-1}$ on A . Due to properties (4) and (5), this equality relation is compatible with the operations in A . Thus, \equiv_{\preceq} is a congruence on A .

In the light of the previous note, it is easy to see that the following applies:

(7) and (8) give:

$$(H3) (\forall x, y, z \in A)(x \cdot y \rightarrow z \equiv_{\preceq} x \rightarrow (y \rightarrow z)).$$

Due to the universality of formula (9), we have:

$$(\forall x, y, z \in A)(x \rightarrow (y \rightarrow z) \equiv_{\preceq} y \rightarrow (x \rightarrow z)).$$

Example 2.3. By a hoop ([3]) we mean an algebra $(H, \cdot, \rightarrow, 1)$ in which $(H, \cdot, 1)$ is a commutative semigroup with the identity and the following assertions are valid:

$$(H1) (\forall x \in H)(x \rightarrow x = 1),$$

$$(H2) (\forall x, y \in H)(x \cdot (x \rightarrow y) = y \cdot (y \rightarrow x)) \text{ and}$$

$$(H3) (\forall x, y, z \in A)(x \cdot y \rightarrow z = x \rightarrow (y \rightarrow z)).$$

In this algebra, order is determined as follows:

$$(\forall x, y \in A)(x \leq y \iff x \rightarrow y = 1).$$

It is easy to see that (H, \leq) is a poset. It is easy to see that every hoop is a (quasi-)ordered residuated system and vice versa does not have to be.

Since, in the general case, the formula

$$(\forall x, y \in A)(x \cdot (x \rightarrow y) \equiv_{\preceq} y \cdot (y \rightarrow x))$$

does not have to be valid in a quasi-ordered residuated system, we conclude that this last mentioned system is a generalization of the hoop-algebra.

Example 2.4. For a commutative monoid A , let $\mathfrak{P}(A)$ denote the powerset of A ordered by set inclusion and \cdot the usual multiplication of subsets of A . Then $\langle \mathfrak{P}(A), \cdot, \rightarrow, A, \subseteq \rangle$ is a quasi-ordered residuated system in which the residuum are given by

$$(\forall X, Y \in \mathfrak{P}(A))(Y \rightarrow X := \{z \in A : Yz \subseteq X\}).$$

Example 2.5. Let $A = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and operations \cdot and \rightarrow defined on A as follows:

\cdot	1	a	b	c	d	and	\rightarrow	1	a	b	c	d
1	1	a	b	c	d		1	1	a	b	c	d
a	a	a	a	a	a		a	1	1	1	1	1
b	b	a	b	b	b		b	1	a	1	1	1
c	c	a	b	c	b		c	1	a	d	1	d
d	d	a	b	b	d		d	1	a	c	c	1

Then $\mathfrak{A} = \langle A, \cdot, \rightarrow, 1 \rangle$ is a quasi-ordered residuated systems where the relation \preceq is defined as follows $\preceq := \{(1, 1), (a, 1), (a, b), (a, c), (a, d), (b, b), (b, c), (b, d), (b, 1), (c, c), (c, 1), (d, d), (d, 1)\}$.

2.2. Concept of filters.

Definition 2.6 ([11], Definition 3.1). For a subset F of a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} we say that it is a *filter* of \mathfrak{A} if it satisfies conditions

$$(F2) (\forall u, v \in A)((u \in F \wedge u \preceq v) \implies v \in F), \text{ and}$$

$$(F3) (\forall u, v \in A)((u \in F \wedge u \rightarrow v \in F) \implies v \in F).$$

Let it note that the empty subset of A satisfies the conditions (F2) and (F3). Therefore, \emptyset is a filter in \mathfrak{A} . It is shown ([11], Proposition 3.4 and Proposition 3.2), that if a non-empty

subset F of a quasi-ordered system \mathfrak{A} satisfies the condition (F2), then it also satisfies the following conditions

- (F0) $1 \in F$ and
(F1) $(\forall u, v \in A)((u \cdot v \in F \implies (u \in F \wedge v \in F))$.

Also, it can be seen without difficulty that $(F3) \implies (F2)$ is valid. Indeed, if (F3) holds, then the formula $u \in F \wedge u \preceq v$, can be transformed into the formula $u \in F \wedge u \rightarrow v \equiv_{\preceq} 1 \in F$ by (F0) so from here, according to (F3) it can be demonstrate the validity of implications (F2). However, the reverse does not have to be valid.

If $\mathfrak{F}(A)$ is the family of all filters in a QRS \mathfrak{A} , then $\mathfrak{F}(A)$ is a complete lattice ([11], Theorem 3.1).

Example 2.7. Let \mathfrak{A} be a quasi-ordered residuated system as in Example 2.5. Then $F_1 := \{1\}$, $F_2 := \{c, 1\}$, $F_3 := \{1, d\}$ and $F_4 := \{1, c, d\}$ and $F_5 := \{1, b, c, d\}$ are filters of \mathfrak{A} .

2.3. Concept of ideals. In the article [13], the concepts of pre-ideal and ideal in quasi-ordered residuated systems were analyzed. Before that, the conditions were analyzed

- (J1) $(\forall y, v \in A)((u \in J \vee v \in J) \implies u \cdot v \in J)$,
(J2) $(\forall u, v \in A)((u \preceq v \wedge v \in J) \implies u \in J)$, and
(J3) $(\forall u, v \in A)((u \rightarrow v \notin J \wedge v \in J) \implies u \in J)$.

Furthermore, in that paper it was proved that (J2) \implies (J1) holds and that (J3) \implies (J2) also holds for the proper subset J . With respect to the above, we have:

Definition 2.8. Let \mathfrak{A} be a quasi-ordered residuated system. For a subset J of the set A we say that it is an pre-ideal in \mathfrak{A} if the condition (J2) is valid. For a subset J of the set A we say that it is an ideal in \mathfrak{A} if $J = A$ or the condition (J3) is valid.

It can easily be seen that if J is a proper (pre-)ideal of \mathfrak{A} , then it holds
(J0) $1 \notin J$.

2.4. Quasi-valuation on QRS. The following definition gives the concept of quasi-valuation maps on a quasi-ordered residuated system.

Definition 2.9. ([14], Definition 3.1) Let $\mathfrak{A} =: \langle A, \cdot, \rightarrow, 1 \rangle$ a quasi-ordered residuated system. A real valued function $v : A / \equiv_{\preceq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called quasi-valuation on \mathfrak{A} if holds

- (V0) $v(1) = 0$ and
(V1) $(\forall x, y \in A)(v(y) \geq v(x) + v(x \rightarrow y))$.

If a quasi-valuation map $v : A / \equiv_{\preceq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfies:

- (V2) $(\forall x \in A)(\neg(x \equiv_{\preceq} 1) \implies v(x) \neq 0)$,

then we say that v is a valuation map on \mathfrak{A} .

In the following proposition, some of the fundamental properties of the mapping $v : A / \equiv_{\preceq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ designed in this way are given .

Proposition 2.2 ([14], Proposition 3.2). *For any quasi-valuation map v on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} , we have the following assertions:*

- (14) $(\forall x, y \in A)(x \preceq y \implies v(x) \leq v(y))$.
(15) $(\forall x \in A)(v(x) \leq 0)$.
(16) $(\forall x, y \in A)(2v(x \cdot y) \leq v(x) + v(y))$.
(17) $(\forall x, y \in A)(v(x \rightarrow y) \leq v(y) - v(x))$.

On the other hand, we have

Proposition 2.3 ([14], Proposition 3.3). *For any quasi-valuation map v on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} , we have the following assertions:*

- (20) $(\forall x, y \in A)(v(x \rightarrow y) \geq v(x) + v(y))$.
 (21) $(\forall x, y \in A)(v(x \cdot y) \geq v(x) + v(y))$.

The following two theorems connect a quasi-valuation $v : A / \equiv_{\leq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} and the concept of filters in \mathfrak{A} .

Theorem 2.4 ([14], Theorem 3.5). *If $v : A / \equiv_{\leq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a quasi-valuation map on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} , then the set*

$$F_v := \{x \in A : v(x) = 0\}$$

is a filter of \mathfrak{A} .

Theorem 2.5 ([14], Theorem 3.6). *Let G be a non-empty filter in a quasi-ordered residuated system $\mathfrak{A} = \langle A, \cdot, 1, \rightarrow \rangle$. For any negative real number k , let v_G be a real valued function on A / \equiv_{\leq} defined by $v_G(x) := 0$ if $x \in G$ and $v_G(x) := k$ if $x \in A \setminus G$. Then v_G is a quasi-valuation on \mathfrak{A} and $F_{v_G} = G$ holds.*

Example 2.10. Let \mathfrak{A} be a quasi-ordered residuated system as in Example 2.5. Then the set $F := \{1, b\}$ is a filter of \mathfrak{A} . If $v : A / \equiv_{\leq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined by $v(1) = v(b) = 0$ and $v(a) = v(c) = v(d) = -7$, then v is a quasi-valuation on \mathfrak{A} according to the Theorem 2.5.

Theorem 2.6 ([14], Theorem 3.8). *If $v : A / \equiv_{\leq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a quasi-valuation map on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} , then the set*

$$J_v := \{x \in A : v(x) < 0\}$$

is an ideal of \mathfrak{A} .

Example 2.11. Let $A = H$ as in article [1], Example 3.3 and let $v : A / \equiv_{\leq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is determined as in Example 3.9 in the same paper. Then v is a quasi-valuation map on \mathfrak{A} . Then $J_v = \{0, a, b\}$ is an ideal and $F_v = \{1\}$ is a filter in \mathfrak{A} because $v(1) = 0$.

In what follows, we will design a pseudo-metric space on a quasi-ordered residuated system generated by a pseudo-valuation on it. By a pseudo-metric on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} , we mean a real-valued function $d : A / \equiv_{\leq} \times A / \equiv_{\leq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfying the following properties: $d(x, y) \geq 0$, $d(x, x) = 0$, $d(x, y) = d(y, x)$ and $d(x, z) \leq d(x, y) + d(y, z)$ for every $x, y, z \in A$. A pseudo-metric d_v on \mathfrak{A} is said to be a metric on \mathfrak{A} and a pseudo metric space (A, d_v) is said to be a metric space if additionally the following holds $(\forall x, y \in A)(d_v(x, y) = 0 \implies x \equiv_v y)$.

Theorem 2.7 ([14], Theorem 3.11). *Let $v : A / \equiv_{\leq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a quasi-valuation on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} . Then*

$$d_v : A / \equiv_{\leq} \times A / \equiv_{\leq} \ni (x, y) \mapsto d_v(x, y) := -(v(x \rightarrow y) + v(y \rightarrow x)) \in \mathbb{R}$$

is a pseudo-metric on \mathfrak{A} and so (A, d_v) is a pseudo-metric space.

3. THE MAIN RESULTS

This section is the main part of this paper. In the first subsection, several important properties of the induced pseudo-metric d_v by quasi-valuation map v in a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} are shown. In the second subsection, we proceed by designing the congruence relation induced by the pseudo-metric d_v .

3.1. Some additional properties of induced pseudo-metric. We begin this subsection with an important result:

Proposition 3.1. *If $v : A/ \equiv_{\prec} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a valuation map on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} , then the pseudo-metric space (A, d_v) induced by v satisfies the following assertion:*

$$(22) (\forall x, y \in A)(d_v(x, y) = 0 \implies x \equiv_{\prec} y).$$

Proof. Let v be a valuation map of a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} . Then v is a quasi-valuation map on \mathfrak{A} . Thus, by Theorem 2.4, d_v is a pseudo-metric. Let $x, y \in A$ be such that $d_v(x, y) = 0$. Then $v(x \rightarrow y) + v(y \rightarrow x) = 0$. Since v is a quasi-valuation map on \mathfrak{A} , for any $u \in A$ holds $v(x) \leq 0$ by (15). So, $v(x \rightarrow y) \leq 0$, $v(y \rightarrow x) \leq 0$ and $v(x \rightarrow y) = -v(y \rightarrow x)$. Thus $0 \geq v(x \rightarrow y) = -v(y \rightarrow x) \geq 0$. Hence $v(x \rightarrow y) = 0 = v(y \rightarrow x)$. From here it follows $x \rightarrow y \equiv_{\prec} 1$ and $y \rightarrow x \equiv_{\prec} 1$ according to the contraposition of (V2). Therefore $x \equiv_{\prec} y$. \square

The following proposition considers the condition when a quasi-valuation map on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} will be a valuation map on \mathfrak{A} .

Proposition 3.2. *Let the pseudo-metric space (A, d_v) induced by a quasi-valuation map $v : A/ \equiv_{\prec} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ in a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} satisfies the condition (22). Then v is a valuation map in \mathfrak{A} .*

Proof. Let the quasi-metric space (A, d_v) induced by a quasi-valuation map $v : A/ \equiv_{\prec} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ in a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} satisfies the condition (22). Let us prove that v satisfies the condition (V2). Let $x \in A$ be such that $v(x) = 0$. Then, from $v(1) + v(x) \leq v(1 \rightarrow x) \leq v(1) - v(x)$ and $v(1) + v(x) \leq v(x \rightarrow 1) \leq v(x) - v(1)$ it follows

$$0 = -2(v(1) + v(x)) \geq -(v(1 \rightarrow x) + v(x \rightarrow 1)) = d_v(1, x) \geq 0.$$

So, $d_v(1, x) = 0$. As (A, d_v) satisfies the condition (22), we get $x \equiv_{\prec} 1$. As (A, d_v) satisfies the condition (22), we get $x \equiv_{\prec} 1$. Thus, we have obtained a contradiction of the formula (V2). This proves that v is a valuation in \mathfrak{A} . \square

The following proposition gives some properties of induced pseudo-metric d_v by a quasi-valuation v on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} .

Proposition 3.3. *Let $v : A/ \equiv_{\prec} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a quasi-valuation map on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} . Then the pseudo-metric space (A, d_v) induced by a quasi-valuation map v satisfies the following assertions:*

- (23) $(\forall x, y, z \in A)(d_v(x, y) \geq d_v(z \rightarrow x, z \rightarrow y))$,
- (24) $(\forall x, y, z \in A)(d_v(x, y) \geq d_v(x \rightarrow z, y \rightarrow z))$,
- (25) $(\forall x, y, z \in A)(d_v(x, y) \geq d_v(z \cdot x, z \cdot y))$.

Proof. Let $v : A/ \equiv_{\prec} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a quasi-valuation map on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} .

For arbitrary elements $x, y, z \in A$,

$$x \rightarrow y \preceq (z \rightarrow x) \rightarrow (z \rightarrow y) \quad \text{and} \quad y \rightarrow x \preceq (z \rightarrow y) \rightarrow (z \rightarrow z)$$

are valid according to (13). Then

$$v(x \rightarrow y) \leq v((z \rightarrow x) \rightarrow (z \rightarrow y)) \quad \text{and} \quad v(y \rightarrow x) \leq v((z \rightarrow y) \rightarrow (z \rightarrow z))$$

also holds by (14). Hence

$$\begin{aligned} d_v(x, y) &= -(v(x \rightarrow y) + v(y \rightarrow x)) \\ &\geq -(v((z \rightarrow x) \rightarrow (z \rightarrow y)) + v((z \rightarrow y) \rightarrow (z \rightarrow z))) \\ &\geq d_v(z \rightarrow x, z \rightarrow y). \end{aligned}$$

This proves the validity of formula (23).

Similarly, we can prove the condition (24) starting from the formula (12).

For arbitrary elements $x, y, z \in A$, the following $x \rightarrow y \preceq x \rightarrow y$ is valid due to the reflexivity of the relation \preceq . Then $(x \rightarrow y) \cdot x \preceq y$ by (3). Thus $(x \rightarrow y) \cdot x \cdot z \preceq y \cdot z$ by (4). From here we get $x \rightarrow y \preceq x \cdot z \rightarrow y \cdot z$ according to (3). Replacing the variables x and y in the previous inequality, we get $y \rightarrow x \preceq y \cdot z \rightarrow x \cdot z$. Now, according to (14), we have $v(x \rightarrow y) \leq v(x \cdot z \rightarrow y \cdot z)$ and $v(y \rightarrow x) \leq v(y \cdot z \rightarrow x \cdot z)$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} d_v(x, y) &= -(v(x \rightarrow y) + v(y \rightarrow x)) \\ &\geq -(v(x \cdot z \rightarrow y \cdot z) + v(y \cdot z \rightarrow x \cdot z)) \\ &= d_v(z \cdot x, z \cdot y). \end{aligned}$$

This proves the inequality (25). \square

3.2. A construction of a congruence induced by a quasi-valuation. In [13], the notion of congruence on a quasi-ordered residuated system was introduced as follows:

Definition 3.1. An equivalence relation θ on a quasi-ordered residuated system $\mathfrak{A} = \langle A, \cdot, \rightarrow, \preceq, 1 \rangle$ is a congruence on \mathfrak{A} if the the following holds

$$\begin{aligned} (\forall x, y, z \in A)((x, y) \in \theta \implies (x \cdot z, y \cdot z) \in \theta) \text{ and} \\ (\forall x, y, z \in A)((x, y) \in \theta \implies ((x \rightarrow z, y \rightarrow z) \in \theta \wedge (z \rightarrow x, z \rightarrow y) \in \theta)). \end{aligned}$$

The following theorem designs an equivalence relation on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} using a quasi-valuation map in \mathfrak{A} .

Theorem 3.4. Let $v : A / \equiv_{\preceq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a quasi-valuation map on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} . Then the relation R_v on A , defined by

$$(\forall x, y \in A)((x, y) \in R_v \iff d_v(x, y) = 0),$$

is an equivalence relation on \mathfrak{A} compatible with the operations in \mathfrak{A} .

Proof. It is clear that R_v is reflexive and symmetric relation on A . Suppose $(x, y) \in R_v$ and $(y, z) \in R_v$. Then $d_v(x, y) = 0$ and $d_v(y, z) = 0$. On the other hand, for arbitrary variables $x, y, z \in A$ $(x \rightarrow y) \cdot (y \rightarrow z) \preceq x \rightarrow z$ holds according to (12). Hence, due to the validity of the implication (14), $v((x \rightarrow y) \cdot (y \rightarrow z)) \preceq v(x \rightarrow z)$ follows. From here, due to (21), we get

$$v(x \rightarrow y) + v(y \rightarrow z) \preceq v((x \rightarrow y) \cdot (y \rightarrow z)) \preceq v(x \rightarrow z).$$

By replacing the variables x and z in the previous formula, we also get

$$v(z \rightarrow y) + v(y \rightarrow x) \preceq v(z \rightarrow x).$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= -d_v(x, y) - d_v(y, z) \\ &= v(x \rightarrow y) + v(y \rightarrow x) + v(y \rightarrow z) + v(z \rightarrow y) \\ &= (v(x \rightarrow y) + v(y \rightarrow z)) + (v(z \rightarrow y) + v(y \rightarrow x)) \\ &\leq v(x \rightarrow z) + v(z \rightarrow x) = -d_v(x, z) \leq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Then $d_v(x, z) = 0$ and so, $(x, z) \in R_v$. Therefore, R_v is a transitive relation on \mathfrak{A} . This shows that R_v is an equivalence relation on A .

Let us prove that R_v is compatible with the operation \rightarrow . For arbitrary elements $x, t, z \in A$ such that $d_v(x, y) = 0$, we have

$$x \rightarrow y \preceq (y \rightarrow z) \rightarrow (x \rightarrow z) \text{ and } y \rightarrow x \preceq (x \rightarrow z) \rightarrow (y \rightarrow z),$$

according to (12). From here, in accordance with (14), we get

$$v(x \rightarrow y) \preceq v((y \rightarrow z) \rightarrow (x \rightarrow z)) \text{ and } v(y \rightarrow x) \preceq v((x \rightarrow z) \rightarrow (y \rightarrow z)).$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= -d_v(x, y) = v(x \rightarrow y) + v(y \rightarrow x) \\ &\leq v((y \rightarrow z) \rightarrow (x \rightarrow z)) + v((x \rightarrow z) \rightarrow (y \rightarrow z)) = -d_v(x \rightarrow z, y \rightarrow z) \\ &\leq v(x \rightarrow z) - v(y \rightarrow z) + v(y \rightarrow z) - v(x \rightarrow z) \quad \text{according to (17)} \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

The second required result $d(z \rightarrow x, z \rightarrow y) = 0$ can be obtained in an analogous way starting with formula (13).

It remains to show that the relation R_v is compatible with the multiplication operation in \mathfrak{A} . Let $x, y, z \in A$ be arbitrary elements such that $d_v(x, y) = 0$. If we start from the valid formula $y \cdot z \preceq y \cdot z$, we get $y \preceq z \rightarrow y \cdot z$ according to (3). From here, according to (13), we get $x \rightarrow y \preceq x \rightarrow (z \rightarrow y \cdot z)$ and from here, according to (8), we have $x \rightarrow y \preceq x \cdot z \rightarrow y \cdot z$. Now, according to (14), we have $v(x \rightarrow y) \preceq v(x \cdot z \rightarrow y \cdot z)$. Therefore, we can now calculate

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= -d_v(x, y) = v(x \rightarrow y) + v(y \rightarrow x) \leq v(x \cdot z \rightarrow y \cdot z) + v(y \cdot z \rightarrow x \cdot z) \\ &= -d_v(x \cdot z, y \cdot z) \leq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $d_v(x \cdot z, y \cdot z) = 0$, which means that $(x \cdot z, y \cdot z) \in R_v$ holds. This proves the compatibility of the relation R_v with the multiplication operation in \mathfrak{A} . \square

The importance of a congruence relation R_v on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} is justified by the fact that the quotient A/R_v turns naturally into an ordered set. It is commonly known that if (A, \preceq) is a quasi-ordered set and R_v is an equivalence relation on A , then the relation \leq , defined by

$$(\forall x, y \in A)([x]_{R_v} \leq [y]_{R_v} \iff x \preceq y)$$

is an order relation on A/R_v . Let us define operations ' \odot ' and ' \Rightarrow ' as

$$\begin{aligned} (\forall x, y \in A)([x]_{R_v} \odot [y]_{R_v} &= [x \cdot y]_{R_v}) \text{ and} \\ (\forall x, y \in A)([x]_{R_v} \Rightarrow [y]_{R_v} &= [x \rightarrow y]_{R_v}). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.5. *Let \mathfrak{A} be a quasi-ordered relational system and let $v : A / \equiv_{\preceq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a quasi-valuation map on \mathfrak{A} . Then*

$$\langle A/R_v, \odot, \Rightarrow, [1]_{R_v}, \leq \rangle$$

is a (quasi-)ordered residuated system.

Proof. This is a special case of Theorem 5.3 in the article [13]. \square

In what follows, we need the following lemma:

Lemma 3.6. *Let $v : A / \equiv_{\preceq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a quasi-valuation map on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} . Then holds*

$$(\forall x \in A)(v(x \rightarrow 1) = 0) \quad \text{and} \quad (\forall x \in A)(v(x) = v(1 \rightarrow x)).$$

Proof. Let $x \in A$ be an arbitrary element. Then $x \preceq 1$ implies $1 \preceq x \rightarrow 1 \preceq 1$. Thus $v(1) \leq v(x \rightarrow 1) \leq v(1)$ by (14). On the other hand, from $x \preceq 1 \rightarrow x$ it follows $v(x) \leq v(1 \rightarrow x) \leq v(x) - v(1) = v(x)$ according to (14) and (17). \square

Theorem 3.7. *Let $v : A / \equiv_{\preceq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a quasi-valuation map on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} . Then $F_v = [1]_{R_v}$ and $J_v = \bigcup_{d_v(x,1) > 0} [x]_{R_v}$.*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Proof. } F_v &= \{x \in A : v(x) = 0\} = \{x \in A : v(1 \rightarrow x) + v(x \rightarrow 1) = 0\} \\ &= \{A : d_v(1, x) = 0\} = \{x \in A : (x, 1) \in R_v\} = [1]_{R_v}. \end{aligned}$$

Also, we have

$$\begin{aligned} J_v &= \{x \in A : v(x) < 0\} = \{x \in A : v(1 \rightarrow x) + v(x \rightarrow 1) < 0\} \\ &= \{x \in A : -d_v(1, x) < 0\} = \{x \in A : d_v(1, x) > 0\} \\ &= \bigcup_{d_v(x,1) > 0} [x]_{R_v}. \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

Let $C(F_v)$ be a relation on \mathfrak{A} defined by

$$(\forall x, y \in A)((x, y) \in C(F_v) \iff (x \rightarrow y \in F_v \wedge y \rightarrow x \in F_v)).$$

On the other hand, we have:

Theorem 3.8. *Let $v : A / \equiv_{\preceq} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a quasi-valuation map on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} . Then $C(F_v) = R_v$.*

Proof. Let $x, y \in A$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (x, y) \in C(F_v) &\iff (x \rightarrow y \in F_v \wedge y \rightarrow x \in F_v) \\ &\iff v(x \rightarrow y) = v(y \rightarrow x) = 0 \\ &\iff v(x \rightarrow y) + v(y \rightarrow x) = 0 \\ &\iff d_v(x, y) = 0 \\ &\iff (x, y) \in R_v. \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

Theorem 3.9. *Let v and w be quasi-valuation maps on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} with $v \neq w$. If $[1]_{R_v} = [1]_{R_w}$, then R_v and R_w coincide and so $A/R_v = A/R_w$.*

Proof. Let $x, y \in A$ such that $(x, y) \in R_v$. Then $d_v(x, y) = 0$ and $v(x \rightarrow y) + v(y \rightarrow x) = 0$. Thus $v(x \rightarrow y) = -v(y \rightarrow x) \geq 0$ by (15). This is possible only if $v(x \rightarrow y) = 0$ and, therefore, $v(y \rightarrow x) = 0$. This means that $x \rightarrow y \in [1]_{R_v}$ and $y \rightarrow x \in [1]_{R_v}$. On the other hand, since $[1]_{R_v} = [1]_{R_w}$ by assumption, we have $x \rightarrow y \in [1]_{R_w}$ and $y \rightarrow x \in [1]_{R_w}$. So, $(x, y) \in R_w$. The reverse implication $R_w \subseteq R_v$ it can be proved analogously to the previous one. Thus $R_v = R_w$. \square

4. CONCLUSIONS

This report is a continuation of papers on our research of quasi-ordered residuated systems. More precisely, this paper is a continuation in the literal sense of the paper [14]. In articles [11, 13] the concepts of filters and ideals in such algebraic structures are analyzed. Article [14] is dedicated to designing the concept of quasi-valuation map in a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} and analyzing its properties. In this paper, a congruence on a quasi-ordered residuated system \mathfrak{A} , generated by a quasi-valuation in \mathfrak{A} , is designed. In addition, it was shown (Theorem 3.9) that if for quasi-valuation maps v and w on a quasi-ordered residual system \mathfrak{A} the following holds $[1]_{R_v} = [1]_{R_w}$, then R_v and R_w coincide.

The author is convinced that the results announced in this report raise academic knowledge about quasi-ordered residuated systems and that they can be one of the bases for further research into these algebraic structures.

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DANIEL A. ROMANO
 INTERNATIONAL MATHEMATICAL VIRTUAL INSTITUTE,
 6, KORDUNAŠKA STREET, 78000 BANJA LUKA, BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA
 ORCID: 0000-0003-1148-3258
 Email address: daniel.a.romano@hotmail.com